

Rwandan girls' experiences of learning in English Medium Secondary Education: Typologies and girls' narratives

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This document presents the typologies and 24 girls' narratives developed through data generation and analysis as part of the ESRC project: *A case study of girls' educational experiences in English medium Rwandan basic education* (ES/S001972/1). Data was generated with 24 girls in 4 schools in the districts of Nyarugenge, Burera, Ruhango and Kirehe. These districts were chosen following descriptive analysis of primary and secondary English examination results, factor analysis of community gender-based attitudes from Household Survey data and descriptive statistics of districts' education, rurality and poverty levels. The districts were:

District	District description	Community gendered attitudes	Enrolment rates	Results in English examinations
Kirehe (Eastern Province)	One of the most rural.	high gender-based bias.	Below average primary enrolment but higher for girls than boys.	Highest proportion of girls 40—49% at P6 English; Highest failure rate for girls at S3 English.
Ruhango (Southern province)	Rural; middling on poverty levels.	lowest gender-based bias in the country.	Highest enrolment at primary; Below average enrolment for secondary (comparable to boys).	Among the lowest failure rates at S3 English for girls (only 6% gap to boys).
Nyarugenge (Kigali)	Richest and urban.	middling for gender-based bias.	Above average primary enrolment; One of the highest secondary enrolment, comparable to boys.	10% distinction at P6 English (but lower than other Kigali districts); Girls outperforming boys in S3 English with highest distinction rates for girls in country.
Burera (Northern province)	One of the most rural; high poverty rates.	higher than average gender-based bias.	One of the highest primary enrolment rates (and higher for girls) but below average enrolment at secondary.	Lowest distinction at S3 English and highest failure gap between boys and girls.

The schools were chosen together with the District Education Officer as broadly reflective of the identified characteristics in the above table. At each school, we worked with the head teacher and senior 3 teachers to identify girls to participate in the research who were broadly representative of the class group as a whole. For example, in Nyarugenge, we identified more girls who were performing academically very well to reflect the higher proportion of girls in that district who scored a distinction in senior 3 examinations in the previous year. Similarly, in Burera, we identified more girls who were at risk of failing their examinations or dropping out.

The 24 girls were given information and consent forms were translated into Kinyarwanda, presented orally and in writing to participants. When they agreed to participate in the study, they were then given a pre-task to note the things that they liked and did not like about their learning, both in school and at home. These were used in place of the originally planned data generation method of photovoice whereby the girls would take photos of the things that were important to them in their learning. We purposefully did not ask the girls to focus on gender and language but instead used the notes they had made as prompts in very loosely structured narrative interviews with the girls. The interviews took place in Kinyarwanda between the girls and Dorimana and Uwizeyemariya (both of whom are female, multilingual Rwandans), outside of lesson time. All interviews were transcribed and translated into English. Alongside interviews, all the girls were also observed in 16 lessons using a dual observation schedule that documented the lesson content, key activities that took place, and the teacher's approach to inclusion and language use alongside a particular focus on the girls' engagement and talk in each lesson.

Interview data was first analysed thematically separately, with Milligan looking for themes related to language of learning and teaching and Sprague looking for gender-related themes. For classroom participation analysis, we coded based on the girls' level of engagement and the amount and type of talk in English they did, noted in observations or through girls' own descriptions of lesson involvement. Following this, we clustered the girls into typologies before mapping these onto the key language-related themes. We identified the following five typologies which we present in this paper:

1. Those at a tipping point
2. Those who are 'at risk'
3. The teachers' favourites
4. Those who use multiple strategies
5. Those going against the odds

We also describe each of the 24 girls based on their interviews, how they were observed in class and where available, the teacher or head teacher's descriptions of each girl.

Those at a tipping point (Amor, Alice, Charity, Gisele, Afta, Honorine)

Overview of the **Tipping Point** typology

General demographics: the six girls were from all four sampled districts (Nyarugenge, Kirehe, Ruhango and Burera) and varied in age from 16 to 19 years old. Most are not able to attend school very regularly.

Attainment: identified by their teachers as girls who are 'doing okay', they are at the tipping point of being able to pass and transition to upper secondary.

In-class activity: their engagement in lessons is inconsistent. They do some limited talk in English in the classroom (e.g. responding in chorus or to closed questions) but do not take any opportunities to develop their language such as through summarising, asking questions or taking risks.

Support mechanisms: these girls mainly talk about the role of their teacher in terms of their code-switching to help them understand curricular content. Their peers are important to them for learning purposes. In all but one case they can be seen taking from peers, so their peers are helping them understand in Kinyarwanda what they are not able to understand from the teacher.

Home life: almost all have significant chores at home. They all have relatively low financial burdens and most live in relatively secure home environments. They all try to revise and some talk about strategies to be able to revise and memorise, such as using music to help with this.

Role of English: English has a significant impact upon these girls. They talk a lot about the importance of teachers explaining to help them understand with some explicitly talking about the role of code switching and the use of Kinyarwanda in that process. They already have a fair amount of burden at home, including house work, but manage to do school revision. The role of English in the classroom might be the thing that tips them into them over the edge into not being able to progress in their schooling. What is keeping them afloat is dependence upon peers who have a better understanding of what is happening in the classroom.

Amor is 16 years old and attends secondary three in Ruhango district, a relatively rural district with middling poverty levels and very low incidences of gender-based bias in the community. Girls in Ruhango had among the lowest average failure rates compared to the national picture and with only a 6% gap in the proportion that passed English compared to boys. Amor attends a school which is rural, but not remote, and where girls and boys have broadly similar English results at the end of both primary and lower secondary school.

Amor was initially selected as one of the girls with the highest achievement, expected by her teachers to gain a merit and transition to upper secondary school. In this way, she is different to other girls in the *Tipping Point* group. Recent changes in her home life mean that things have changed. There is a lot of difficulty at home since her father has started sleeping at a neighbour's house and being with the woman in that home whose husband has gone to prison. This has led to a lot of conflict at home. She describes the neighbour woman as her husband's

concubine. She says that he gets drunk and beats her mother. Anour says that her mother is not happy and that her father is not contributing. She says that everything has changed, that he no longer encourages her to study as he used to before. She conveys a lot of sorrow from her home situation and has been worried that she will lose interest in everything, including school.

This situation has contributed to a recent drop in school performance in the last trimester because it happened when she was about to start exams and she was not able to revise. She wanted to stay home and help her mother on the farm, but her mother and aunt have told her to stay in school and study harder and that if she is lucky to finish her studies and get a job, this will help to support her mother and show her father that they can survive without him. She does try to help her mother by collecting food and grasses for the cows and to help by cooking but sometimes her mother tells her to revise her lessons and does these home chores alone. Her home situation has also had a significant impact on her concentration and engagement in class. While she still speaks more than other girls in this typology, including raising her hand and responding to questions in Chemistry and History and Citizenship, she is also described by the researchers as 'not active', 'too quiet' and 'just following' in both Biology and Geography. In History & Citizenship, it was also noted that she was writing explanations while the teacher was talking. During activities, Amor was observed to be engaged in all lessons except Geography, when she was described as 'distracted' and it was observed that she was copying explanations. In Biology, Chemistry, and History & Citizenship her engagement with the activity was shown by the fact that she was writing.

Amor says that school is the place that relieves her from the troubles between her parents, that it is her second home. Amor feels joy at being with other learners in school. She has a variety of friends and appreciates their diversity. When she wants to study, she joins those who work hard and who understand the material. When she wants to play, she joins in with those who also like to play. Amor appreciates her friends who tell stories and jokes and joins them when she wants to relax. She also appreciates her teachers and finds that each of them has something that she likes. Amor refers to her teachers as being like parents and acknowledges that each of them is different. Despite difficult circumstances, Amor seems to convey a great deal of happiness and joy as well as sorrow. She talks about playing with classmates and having times when she can relax. Her mother encourages her to focus on her studies, but she is worried that the family situation will lead to her losing interest in school. It seems that her friendship bonds and her female family bonds are quite strong and important.

Alice attends secondary three in Ruhango district, a relatively rural district with middling poverty levels and very low incidences of gender-based bias in the community. Girls in Ruhango had among the lowest average failure rates compared to the national picture and with only a 6% gap in the proportion that passed English compared to boys. Amor attends a school which is rural, but not remote, and where girls and boys have broadly similar English results at the end of both primary and lower secondary school. Alice is expected to 'just pass' her English 3 examinations. She is sometimes absent from school because she helps her father at home since her mother passed away.

Alice lives with her father and younger brother. She does all the housework, which she says she likes, but sometimes her father helps her and then encourages her to do her revision. There is a garden at home, and she enjoys sitting out among the flowers and grasses and revising when the sun is out, and she sits under a tree. She complains that nutrition at home gets in the way of her studies because there are foods she cooks, such as cassava paste, which makes her sleepy. She admits that there is a lot of housework to do, such as cooking, sweeping, fetching water and harvesting and that sometimes she doesn't have the energy to study after all of that. She particularly dislikes harvesting beans because that makes her especially tired. She has a desk and notebooks at home, and she tries to study from 8:30

to 9:30 at night. She is sometimes distracted by worrying about her father when he stays out late and doesn't ring to say when he will be home.

Alice revises at school with two of her friends. They meet to study together in the morning from 7-8AM. Alice says that at that time, there was no sun, and she feels the courage to study. She says these friends help her with the difficult lessons and one of the girls is a neighbour and the other lives far from her home, so they meet at school to revise. She enjoys history class, partly because she likes the way the teacher teaches. She explains that he translates from English to Kinyarwanda or mixes the two languages to help them understand. She also likes math and Kinyarwanda, English, entrepreneurship and history. She likes math because it helps her to see new things. She recounts that in primary school she was told that 2-5 was impossible, but now she sees that this is possible (presumably in reference to negative numbers). She realises that this kind of information can help with doing business. She feels that the lessons help her to have self-confidence in real life situations. On the other hand, she feels that she lacks confidence in physics and sometimes mathematics because she feels unable to achieve and says these are boys' subjects. She prefers to study Kinyarwanda and history, particularly the ancients because she enjoys learning about where she has come from, how people in the past lived and the technology they had.

She receives food at school through the school feeding programme and she feels this helps her to study without worry. She likes that at school there is a facility where she can get cleaned when she's menstruating. She says this saves her time. She says she enjoys working with colleagues at school, including discussions among one another, but hates noise and peer pressure. She comments also that learning is difficult at school when she is menstruating and she lacks materials, so she asks to be released to go home.

Alice is inconsistent in her attention and talk in class. She often is observed just trying to follow what the teacher says to keep up. In the Chemistry lesson, she was observed reading her notebook while the teacher was talking, and she raised her hand to answer questions but was not selected. In Geography, she was similarly observed checking her notes. She raised her hand to contribute to the characteristics of the savanna. Alice was described as 'engaged' in all activities, except in Chemistry, when the observer noted that she was distracted and reading her notebook. In Biology, she reads the question aloud in the public talk and she was observed as following the presentation and writing.

Charity is 17 years old and attends secondary three in Burera, one of the most rural and poorest districts in Rwanda where gender-based bias is amongst the highest in the country. While enrolment is very high for girls in Burera at primary level, this changes in lower secondary where the enrolment rate is below average for girls and boys. Girls in Burera have the lowest chance of a distinction at S3 English or anywhere in the country and the widest failure gap between boys and girls. Charity's school is very rural and in an area of high poverty. Girls at the school also have high demands on their time due to household chores, often missing parts of the school day. This includes Charity whose home chores impact her attendance and study time, in turn meaning that she is at risk of not passing her Secondary 3 examinations.

Charity talks a lot about the different things that help or prevent her in her learning. For example, she likes it when her teachers give her exercises because without them, she would not open her notebook. The exercises help her to revise her lessons and improve her thinking and knowledge. She arrives at school around 7:40, missing the compulsory self-study time because of the heavy housework responsibility. She gets in trouble for not completing her homework because there is not enough time to finish it before the teachers arrive at 8:00. She doesn't like being frightened by teachers. Her entrepreneurship teacher surprises them,

coming up behind them and seeing them taking notes of other lessons. He beats them with a stick or with his hand on their heads. This prevents her from learning his lessons well.

Charity likes Biology because it helps her to understand her own body and how to care for herself. She also likes the way her Biology teacher teaches and how he puts them in small groups. When they make summaries and present the information, she finds this helps her remember because when you present something it is not easily forgotten. Charity finds it difficult when she has lost notes or when students steal pens, particularly at the end of the trimester, and she cannot finish her work without these things. She is distracted by students at school who make noise and prevent her from studying well because she cannot revise. She says she wants to use the time at school well, but when students make noise, it prevents her.

She is encouraged by students who can speak English without difficulty. She says that when they are asked questions in English and fail to understand them in Kinyarwanda but can find a student who does understand this encourages her to try harder next time. She describes also when they are in small groups during exercises 'you must understand them in order to find what to say in front of others.' Some students will not explain everything in Kinyarwanda, and this encourages her to learn so that she can explain to herself what was not translated.

During lessons, Charity is observed as being engaged in the Biology lesson, both during the teacher-led work and during activities. During the pair activity she was observed discussing with her partner in Kinyarwanda. In the other 3 lessons, Charity is described as 'passive' and 'silent'. In Geography it is noted that she is 'sometimes distracted' during the teacher-led work. In the Geography activities, she did not raise her hand to volunteer an answer, but when she was called upon by the teacher, the observer has noted that she responded surprisingly well when asked to give one factor influencing the development of industry. She offered a correct answer, 'availability of capital', but she was not able to explain this, and a boy volunteered to explain instead.

Charity likes to help her parents with the housework. She says she likes to be patient with the housework and she cannot refuse to help her parents because they pay her school fees. She is responsible for cooking, fetching water and looking for grasses for the cow. She gets up at 5:40 so she can do these chores and take care of fertilizer or beans and sweeps the floor before going to school. She tries to do the work quickly so there will be time for revising. Sometimes her parents refuse to leave the lights on because they are going to sleep. She finds that when she uses the torch for light to study, she sometimes falls asleep before turning it off and then the battery is dead in the morning. Sometimes also she is tired, so she does not revise for these reasons. Sometimes she revises in the morning if there is no housework, but when she is told to carry the fertilizer, she does not have time for morning study and also, she is late to school. When she does find time to revise, Charity relies on music to help her memorise. She acknowledges that it is difficult to memorise something in English if you do not understand the content or understand the meaning in Kinyarwanda, so she uses music to help her overcome this. She also says she is 'distracted' when at home she cannot read and translate for herself from English to Kinyarwanda.

Gisele is 17 years old and attends secondary three in a rural school in one of the most rural districts in Rwanda – Kirehe. In Kirehe, there are higher than average community-based gender biases and enrolment rates are lower for both girls and boys than the national average. The vast majority of girls are scoring a 40-49% in the P6 English exam; by S3, Kirehe has the highest failure rate in the English exam for anywhere in the country. This would suggest that English language is a particularly major barrier to learning in this district, with many girls 'just passing' moving into 'failing' by the end of S3. Teachers at Gisele's school suggest that girls

are more affected by both the language of learning and teaching and out-of-school factors than boys. They say that girls face more disturbances such as being harassed by boys/men and family conflict. Early marriage and unplanned pregnancy also impact girls in the school.

Gisele hopes to pass her Secondary three examinations but it is clear that a lot of home chores mean she is worried she will not achieve this. Gisele is the eldest child at home. She does all the work at home, including fetching water, collecting food from the field, and washing dishes. Sometimes others help her to fetch more water or to sweep and then she does the cooking. She says that she likes nothing at home, and she hates having too much work, which causes her to not revise, yet her mother encourages her to study. She is bothered by the lack of money to pay school fees or buy materials for school. Her housework and not having a clock makes her late for school. She tries to revise around 6 or 7pm because she is motivated to do so, but by 9pm she is sleeping. Gisele used to have a boyfriend but stopped because this was getting in the way of school.

Gisele likes studying and reading. She arrives at 6AM to study while it is still quiet but is late for school about once a week because of housework and not having a watch. She revises her lessons while she is at school but cannot revise them all. She uses the break time to revise the upcoming lessons of the day because there is not time to revise at home due to the amount of housework. The noise at school disrupts her and she says that some students don't know what they need from school, but she wants to study in a quiet place. She is encouraged to study through the goals she sets, and these push her to revise the lessons. She thinks a lot about when her parents delay paying her school fees as this demotivates her because she thinks about being chased due to unpaid fees.

Gisele is observed as being actively engaged in the Maths lesson and the observer notes her attempts to participate. She raised her hand to answer closed questions and was selected to give a solution to one of the questions on the board. In History & Citizenship, she does read from her notebook and volunteer an answer to a question about dictators, but when the teacher is talking, she is described as 'mostly disengaged and bored'. In Geography, she is described as 'engaged' when the teacher is leading, and it is noted that she is reading her notes. But during Geography activities she is not actively participating. It is noted that she is sometimes looking through her notes, but other times is engaged in off-task chatting with a boy sitting near her.

Afta is nineteen years old and attends secondary three in Nyarugenge, one of three districts in the capital city of Kigali and the richest district in the country. Nyarugenge has one of the highest enrolment rates in the country for girls in Primary and lower Secondary. One in ten girls scored a distinction in the 2018 Primary Six English National Examinations and distinction rates were also the highest in the country for girls in the Secondary three English National Examinations. Afta attends a school where girls are outperforming boys in English at both the primary and lower secondary levels, although she is only scoring 'just pass' marks.

She lives with her parents and is the fourth of five children. While she says that she tries to concentrate hard on her studies, she is identified by teachers as someone with poor attendance and concentration. However, when we observed her in class she is mostly concentrating on the tasks. She spends a lot of her time writing down the notes from the board. For example, in Biology she is observed copying notes from one notebook to another and in Geography she was reading her notes. She does not choose to speak in teacher-led parts of lessons but during the group activity in the History and Citizenship class, she is seen to be collaborating with Honorine. She speaks some limited English when she presents the group's findings back to the class.

At home, she says that her parents and brother support her in her learning, although she does not give examples. She says she has to spend a lot of time helping to look after younger family members, especially when her mother is at work. She finds some time to study and revise. She cites music as important in helping her to understand more easily. She talks a lot about being worried about getting distracted because of 'the chaos at home', such as movies, neighbours and family members. Similarly, at school she is often worried that noise and other students will distract her.

Afta likes to study at school in the morning from 7:20am because her brain is fresh, and she is not tired. She talks a lot about the role of group work in helping her to understand better because 'she loves when she is understanding what she is taught'. Her favourite subject is History and Citizenship (HAC) because she says her teacher teaches very well and does not only speak English. She mixes in Kinyarwanda, and this is helpful because there are technical words which she does not yet know and when the teacher speaks Kinyarwanda, she can get the vocabulary. The examples she gives include 'insect' because this word in HAC is different from the word in Biology. Also, a word like 'effect' which she used to confuse with 'consequences', but she learned the meaning when the teacher translated it from Kinyarwanda. There are no significant reasons for Afta to be 'at the tipping point' other than her self-cited reliance on code-switching to keep up with curricular content. The impact of learning in English is clear.

Honorine is a very shy nineteen-year-old who dreams of becoming a nurse because she likes Chemistry and Maths. She attends secondary three in Nyarugenge, although she is often absent from school because she has unpaid school contribution fees including for the school feeding programme. Nyarugenge is one of three districts in the capital city of Kigali and the richest district in the country. Nyarugenge has one of the highest enrolment rates in the country for girls in Primary and lower Secondary. One in ten girls scored a distinction in the 2018 Primary Six English National Examinations and distinction rates were also the highest in the country for girls in the Secondary three English National Examinations. Honorine attends a school where girls are outperforming boys in English at both the primary and lower secondary levels, although she is only scoring 'just pass' marks.

Honorine lives far away from school and says that she is often late because of this. This upsets her because she wants to attend the quiet revision hour before school because she says that the quiet helps her to study. For the same reason, she likes to use the school library whenever she is able. She talks a lot about the importance of understanding and having someone to explain the school content to her, although she is not explicit that this is because of the language used. In class, she is generally quiet, copying from the board, and trying to follow what the teacher is saying against the words in the book. She is sometimes talking to her neighbours. In Biology, she is more focused and raises her hand to contribute successfully to a closed question. However, when she was called upon randomly, she was not able to give a correct answer. She contributes during the group work activity in History and Citizenship (although it is not clear which language this discussion happens in). She presented some simple sentences in English with Afta about the effects of the Second World War.

Honorine says she feels motivated to learn by her parents and when people at school say nice words to her, although she does not make it clear whether this is teachers or her peers. She does say that her peers often distract her by chatting and telling stories. She also talks about being distracted from her studies at home by people that live with her, although she gets some time and space to revise. Honorine has housework that sometimes gets in the way of her studying. They have a house girl, but sometimes she needs to do things, and Honorine ends up taking her place and doing the housework after school, or sometimes she arrives home to work that is waiting for her.

Those who are 'at risk' (Elise, Rosine, Rita, Winny, Rose, Fike, Chanise)

Overview of the **At risk** typology

General demographics: the seven girls were from the three rural districts (Nyarugenge, Kirehe, Ruhango and Burera) and varied in age from 16 to 19 years old. Most are not able to attend school very regularly.

Attainment: identified by their teachers as girls who are unlikely to pass their secondary three examinations and who may dropout before the end of lower secondary (including one girl who has already dropped out).

In-class activity: in the classroom, they are observed as either partially engaged or disengaged. They are almost entirely silent with no opportunities to speak in English.

Support mechanisms: these girls mainly see school as a social and safe place away from their difficulties at home and appreciate their peers, especially, as their friends. Group work time involves trying to understand basic content with other girls in a similar boat and socialising.

Home life: Almost all of these girls live in insecure home environments alongside high financial challenges or household chores. Examples here include a girl whose mother had sustained a missed miscarriage and now must do almost all of the home chores to support the household, and another girl whose father is an alcoholic.

Role of English: Learning in English is one of many burdens for these girls. They are dependent on the classroom space for language development and curricular access but have almost no opportunity to talk.

Elise is 17 years old and attends secondary three in a rural school in one of the most rural districts in Rwanda – Kirehe. In Kirehe, there are higher than average community-based gender biases and enrolment rates are lower for both girls and boys than the national average. The vast majority of girls are scoring a 40-49% in the P6 English exam; by S3, Kirehe has the highest failure rate in the English exam for anywhere in the country. This suggests that English language is a particularly major barrier to learning in this district, with many girls 'just passing' moving into 'failing' by the end of S3. Teachers at Elise's school suggest that girls are more affected by both the language of learning and teaching and out-of-school factors than boys. They say that girls face more disturbances such as being harassed by boys/men and family conflict. Early marriage and unplanned pregnancy also impact girls in the school.

Elise lives with her older brother and her mother in a part of town which Elise describes as a bad place near bars which are noisy with people fighting at night. Her father used to live with them, and her parents used to quarrel a lot. Elise talks a lot about how noise and distractions in the home and the surrounding area make it hard for her to concentrate on any schoolwork. She also does a lot of chores in the home which distract her from the one hour she tries to set aside for work.

Her home is financially precarious, and her mother finds it hard to pay Elise's school fees. She says she is motivated to try to learn because she worries that her low grades mean that her mother will not pay her school fees. She often misses school time because of lacking school fees and talks about relying on her peers to explain what she missed when she was not in

class. Elise has a tumor on her hips and finds it difficult to sit for long periods of time in class. This also means that she regularly misses class because when she becomes too uncomfortable, she will not attend until she recovers. She says that the main thing that prevents her from learning well is lacking the school fees. When there is rain, this also affects her route to and from school and she is often late for lessons. On days when it is not raining, she enjoys playing ball or two small stones (a throwing game) and she says it helps her to forget the problems she is facing.

Elise does not talk very much about learning and lessons but says she likes English, Maths, Chemistry and Biology lessons. She says that you need to choose the lessons that you understand and then focus your attention on those. However, in lessons, Elise is observed as consistently not actively engaged and listening silently. She does attempt to follow some of what the teacher is saying and writing on the board in Maths and History and Citizenship lessons. During activities in the Chemistry lesson, Elise is sometimes observed as disengaged and looking out the window. In Geography, it is noted that, during activities she is talking with Rosine and Aurore in Kinyarwanda.

Rosine is 16 years old and attends secondary three in a rural school in one of the most rural districts in Rwanda – Kirehe. In Kirehe, there are higher than average community-based gender biases and enrolment rates are lower for both girls and boys than the national average. The vast majority of girls are scoring a 40-49% in the P6 English exam; by S3, Kirehe has the highest failure rate in the English exam for anywhere in the country. This would suggest that English language is a particularly major barrier to learning in this district, with many girls ‘just passing’ moving into ‘failing’ by the end of S3. Teachers at Elise’s school suggest that girls are more affected by both the language of learning and teaching and out-of-school factors than boys. They say that girls face more disturbances such as being harassed by boys/men and family conflict. Early marriage and unplanned pregnancy also impact girls in the school.

Rosine used to perform well at school, including passing English, but her performance has dropped due to family issues. Her parents are separated, and she lives with her mother and younger siblings. Her mother has had some significant health issues leaving Rosine to take on the family responsibilities as the eldest sister and acting as a carer for her mother. She finds it hard to pay for her school fees. She recently dropped out of school for a month but returned, although it is unclear how long she will remain in school because she cannot get school or lunch fees. She likes chatting with her mother because she says she gets good advice about how to behave and talking with her mother makes her happy. She says that the lack of capacity to pay school fees and being from a poor family makes her learning difficult and that family issues have disrupted her learning and she is not learning well.

She tries to do the housework quickly so there is time to revise. When she is done with her work, she goes directly to revise by giving herself some exercises and focuses on Maths, Physics, Chemistry and Biology. She tries to revise from 8-9pm. However, there is no light at home and her father used to give her a torch, but she does not have access to this now. On the way to and from school, she says she dislikes getting attention from boys.

When she can attend school, she often comes late (at around 8.30am when others start at 7.20am) because she must do the domestic work in the home and sometimes must engage in money-making activities to support her family. Rosine says she doesn’t receive enough facilitation at school when she is menstruating because the time given to shower is very short, so she goes back home and misses a lot until she returns to school.

Rosine’s favourite thing about school is that she likes seeing her friends and socialising with them without divisions. She enjoys maths, physics, biology, chemistry and English because

these are the subjects related to nursing. She wants to be a nurse due to the experience she has had with her sick brother and mother, but she does not expect to be able to continue into S4.

Rosine says she hates asking questions to the teachers during lessons when they answer back that she should ask her classmates. She wants a direct answer because she says her classmates have the same questions and problems understanding and therefore, they leave the topic without understanding. Rosine says that when she tries to explain to her teacher the challenges she is facing, he refuses to accept it, so she continues to learn with difficulty.

During classroom observations, Rosine is only observed to be engaged in the Maths lesson, in the other 3 lessons she is described as 'silent', 'looking absent-minded', 'disengaged', 'not engaged'. In the Mathematics lesson she was selected to respond to one of the evaluation questions. In the Geography lesson, it was noted that she was only engaged in the evaluation activity. In Chemistry and History & Citizenship, Rosine is observed not to be following and to be distracted. In Chemistry she was looking through a book (observation notes imply not directly related to the lesson) and chatting off-topic ('disturbing') with the girl next to her. She was also one of the group of 3 case-study students noted to be chatting during activities in the Geography lesson.

Rita attends secondary three in Burera, one of the most rural and poorest districts in Rwanda where gender-based bias is amongst the highest in the country. While enrolment is very high for girls in Burera at primary level, this changes in lower secondary where the enrolment rate is below average for girls and boys. Girls in Burera have the lowest chance of a distinction at S3 English or anywhere in the country and the widest failure gap between boys and girls. Rita's school is very rural and in an area of high poverty. Girls at the school also have high demands on their time due to household chores, often missing parts of the school day.

Rita is described by her teachers as a poor performer who does not make any effort to improve. Her teachers do not show any awareness of out-of-school problems. Rita lives with her five siblings and both parents. She does not talk much about her home life apart from talking about doing a lot of housework. She is responsible for collecting grass for two cows and fetching water in the morning before getting her younger sibling ready for primary school and taking that sibling to school before she can herself go to school. The schools are in opposite directions. Due to all this work, she gets up at 4:30 but does not arrive at school before 7:30. She says that she also collects grass and fetches water in the afternoon after school.

She likes to study Biology at home because she finds it easy, and she can do this in the short time available to her for revision. She studies at home around 8pm after her chores. Rita appreciates that they have a solar panel at home, which provides electricity so she can study in the evening. Her parents also encourage her to study and tell her that if she works hard to succeed in the national examination to be admitted they will pay the school fees. However, she finds her younger sister distracting because she wants to play with her and this keeps her from learning.

Rita likes to study Geography. She says that when the teacher gives explanations, it is hard for her to get something and so she revises many times. This revising helps her to like it. She likes it when students help each other. Her friends encourage her to study. They ask each other what they did not capture well during learning, and this helps motivate her to learn. She likes to revise Kinyarwanda with colleagues because this is the lesson she can communicate easily about. She says that other lessons are difficult to revise because the language is also hard. She finds it distracting when classmates come to school with cell phones that have

memory cards because she then watches songs and movies with them. Rita shares that there are also some boys who come to school drunk, and they disturb the others.

On the way to and from school, Rita regularly encounters drunk people, mostly boys, who hold sticks and tell her that learning is a waste of time. She says that when they don't respond to them, they make them run, threatening to beat them. She wishes that someone would prevent her from meeting violent people on the way to and from school.

During classroom observations, Rita is not observed as being engaged in any of the 4 lessons. The word 'silent' is used to describe her in 5 out of 8 situations. During activities in Biology it is noted that she 'looks distracted (absent minded)' and in History & Citizenship it is observed that she 'looks as if she has no concentration on the lesson'. In the Geography lesson, although she does not volunteer, she is selected by the teacher to summarise the lesson and she did this, speaking for 3 minutes giving a lesson summary in English. This suggested that, although she had been very quiet, she had been listening (she had been observed looking at the teacher and making some notes).

Winnie is eighteen years old and attends secondary three in Burera, having repeated a number of years. Burera is one of the most rural and poorest districts in Rwanda where gender-based bias is amongst the highest in the country. While enrolment is very high for girls in Burera at primary level, this changes in lower secondary where the enrolment rate is below average for girls and boys. Girls in Burera have the lowest chance of a distinction at S3 English or anywhere in the country and the widest failure gap between boys and girls. Winnie's school is very rural and in an area of high poverty. Girls at the school also have high demands on their time due to household chores, often missing parts of the school day.

Winnie lives with her parents who find it hard to pay school or lunch fees. She regularly has to miss school because she needs to help with money-making activities with her parents. Winnie seems to have mixed feelings about her home responsibilities. She says she enjoys helping her parents at home with tasks like cooking and looking for cows' grasses in order that they pay her school fees. At another time, she says that she hates these responsibilities and has too much work, which makes her tired and then she cannot revise well. Sometimes she makes extra money by fetching water or taking care of the cow fertilizer. Her parents encourage her to study, particularly her father. He helps to find people to help her study and to help her with lessons at home as well as explaining to her what he understands. She says she has colleagues who help her revise lessons at home. At home, she revises from 8-10 pm, despite the fact that they do not have electricity. She manages to study by torchlight. She doesn't have time to study in the morning. When she eats and gets full, this encourages her to revise her lessons.

Winnie says that the distance to school is too long, around one hour, and this makes her late and disturbs her learning. She likes to go with students because they help each other to understand the content. She likes to revise History and Geography on the way to and from school. She dislikes the road to school because it is muddy with rain, and she hates to go home in that situation.

Winnie says she enjoys classes and all teachers. She says she enjoys Biology, Math and English because she feels that she will benefit from them if she learns them well. She says that these teachers teach well so that she can understand, and this is why she likes their lessons at school. She values Biology because it helps to learn about her own life and her reproductive health, including how she can do prevention. She values Math because she wants to work at a bank. She values English because she knows that she may need these language skills for employed work. She says she doesn't know her future yet and they may

tell her that to do a particular job she will need to speak English well. She mentions that there are students at school who attend unwillingly, and they want other students to make stories (unclear about what). She hates students who want her to make up a story and finds that this makes her forget what she has learnt.

In classroom observations, Winny is mostly described as 'silent', 'passive', and 'not actively engaged'. She is also observed to be silent during activities. In the Biology lesson, there was a pair activity, but Winny was not observed speaking. In History & Citizenship she was observed taking some notes, but again she was silent.

Rose is seventeen years old and attends secondary three in Burera, one of the most rural and poorest districts in Rwanda where gender-based bias is amongst the highest in the country. While enrolment is very high for girls in Burera at primary level, this changes in lower secondary where the enrolment rate is below average for girls and boys. Girls in Burera have the lowest chance of a distinction at S3 English or anywhere in the country and the widest failure gap between boys and girls. Rose's school is very rural and in an area of high poverty. Girls at the school also have high demands on their time due to household chores, often missing parts of the school day.

Rose lives with her mother and has a father who has two wives, so he is present only part of the time. This causes conflict at home and her parents argue. Rose explains that her boyfriend takes advantage of that situation to encourage her to come away with him and to marry and create and work for their own family. She has one brother also at home. Rose enjoys listening to music, particularly gospel and Rwandan music as this helps her to relax. She listens to these songs when she is in the kitchen cooking. She is the main cook for the family and says that this is her duty because this is girls' work, and she is the only remaining girl at home. Her brother has duties pertaining to the livestock such as collecting food for the animals, milking the cows and helping their father at his mill. Rose is responsible for gathering food from the field, preparing and cooking the foods, and doing some cultivating when she hasn't gone to school. There is some tension between her and her mother, who criticizes Rose for delaying her cooking. Rose explains that she is very busy with domestic chores and is working hard. She doesn't seem to understand why her mother criticises her and she feels that the distribution of work favours her brother and finds this unfair. She mentions that she is the one who has to carry manure on her head, that he cannot manage to do this and only helps with this chore when he has a bicycle. She rarely revises for lessons at home because she is typically busy with housework until 9PM and feels exhausted and cannot revise.

Rose does not attend school regularly and her teachers say that this impacts her performance. She is described by her teachers as careless and a learner who does not make any effort to improve. Rose seems to miss a lot of school because of her period and not having pads because her parents cannot purchase them and sometimes the school doesn't have them either. When this happens, she goes home and doesn't return until her period is over. Rose likes doing exercises during free time at school because at this time she can work with classmates who help her to understand the lessons. She does not mention going to school early for self-study or staying after school for this, either. Rose appreciates the company of her friends on the way to and from school. The journey to and from school presents Rose with some difficult peer pressure situations. She describes that there are boys who come looking for girlfriends and they want her to stop and talk and that this delays her. Refusing to stop and chat results in insults.

Rose seems to look forward to school as a break from her domestic work, saying that when she is at school, she can relax a bit. She mentions that a Chemistry teacher is responsible for serving as a mentor/advisor to a group of girls. This teacher comes and dismisses the boys, and the girls have discussions about reproductive health and the teacher offers guidance and

advice. Rose is in the class choir, which she says helps her to feel attached to her school. She misses her classmates and school during the holiday times or any time they are not going to school. Rose seems to value her friendships, commenting that she likes chatting with other learners and this is sometimes about lessons, but they share other stories, too, some which include reproductive related issues. She says they talk about their life and friendship experiences. She says she likes school because without it, she wouldn't have met these friends. She says that some of the girls want to have boyfriends and that they want other girls to be like them and they want to discuss it at break and go to the toilet together to share stories, yet she says this disturbs her. Academically, she enjoys Maths because it doesn't require much speaking or writing. She comments that other subjects have a lot more complicated English to read and memorize. She dislikes noise in class from other students because it prevents her from learning, and they get punished for it. She specifically mentions that she likes English because it is a Language of Instruction, and she knows that if she knew English better it would help her to understand other subjects. It seems possible that she is simply not accessing the content of other subjects because of the language barrier. She says she is not good at English and compares herself to her brother who is in S2 but is 'better' than her because he speaks English with teachers and the director of studies which has built up his confidence and helped him improve his English skills. During classroom observations, Rose is mostly described as 'silent' although the observer suggests that she is actively listening and she is noted to be looking in her exercise book during activities in Biology, Geography and History & Citizenship, including taking notes in H&C. In Biology, she is selected to answer a question – she reads the answer from her notebook.

Fike used to attend secondary three in Ruhango district but left the school during the period of fieldwork due to pregnancy. Ruhango is a relatively rural district with middling poverty levels and very low incidences of gender-based bias in the community. Girls in Ruhango had among the lowest average failure rates compared to the national picture and with only a 6% gap in the proportion that passed English compared to boys. Fike used to attend a school which is rural, but not remote, and where girls and boys have broadly similar English results at the end of both primary and lower secondary school. Before Fike left the school, she was identified by her teachers as someone who had low performance, attending school only regularly but when she was in class, was someone who participated. Her teachers say that she lived in a home where she often was alone. While we did not interview Fike or observe her in lessons, we choose to continue to include her story for her, and the many other Rwandan girls, who are not able to complete their basic education.

Chanise attends secondary three in Ruhango district, a relatively rural district with middling poverty levels and very low incidences of gender-based bias in the community. Girls in Ruhango had among the lowest average failure rates compared to the national picture and with only a 6% gap in the proportion that passed English compared to boys. Chanise attends a school which is rural, but not remote, and where girls and boys have broadly similar English results at the end of both primary and lower secondary school. Chanise is identified by teachers as one of the girls at risk of dropout due to poor attendance and low grades, she is predicted to fail her S3 English examination.

Chanise is the third of five children. Her older brother, the first born, stopped his studies at P4. Her sister, the second born stopped at P6. She has reached S3 with difficulty, having repeated P2 and P3 but says that she is the most advanced in her family. She wants to continue with her studies in order to be different from her other family members who didn't benefit from schooling. Her home life is financially precarious. When she gets something to do for money such as cleaning, assisting in constructions by carrying bricks, she does not attend school. She explained that her attendance has been particularly impacted by the school closures due

to the Covid-19 pandemic when she had to do some paid work which continued even when schools reopened.

Chanise says that her mother is a caring parent who helps her get what she needs for school. She says her mother doesn't have enough means to cater for their needs, but she does have a goat and sells the kids to get priority materials such as her uniform, pens and pencils. She says that when her mother doesn't have money 'we bear with her'. From time to time, Chanise helps her mother on the farm, particularly during the rainy season. She helps with cleaning and grass collecting for the cows and also with cultivation. By contrast, she finds her father to be unsupportive and unwilling to give money. She says her father's money is for beer only. She feels that he doesn't care about her wellbeing nor about her education. She says he doesn't care if she drops out or stays in school. She conveys that he gets drunk and interrupts her home study with his loud and insulting behaviour, that instead of studying, she goes to bed immediately in order to leave him alone. She feels that his behaviour interferes with her exam preparation. Chanise has a boyfriend who is a neighbour. She describes that he dropped out when in S2 but says they don't discuss school. At home, she sometimes studies by lamp and torch in the evening between 7 and 8pm, but not at the weekend. She describes that during the exam period, she tries to revise in the evening, but without these things, she cannot.

Chanise says she enjoys playing and chatting with her classmates. She describes that when the teacher is not present, her classmates shout, that they like telling stories that are not related to the lessons and this gets in the way of self-study. She tries harder to understand Maths and Kinyarwanda compared to other subjects. She finds Chemistry difficult and says she doesn't understand it.

On the way to and from school, she enjoys being with other learners because they discuss their life experiences. She says she has friends who share during these trips about their boyfriends and sometimes they get boyfriends on the way. She says that the way to and from school is important but also is a disturbance and distracting. It's a long journey to school, around two hours. She leaves home at 5:30 or 6 to be there for 7:30. Because of the long journey, she often doesn't go when it's raining. She describes passing past households where people quarrel, children play and where drunkards get her attention and delay her.

During classroom observations, Chanise was absent from the Biology lesson, when it was noted there was heavy rain. She was also absent from the Geography lesson. In Chemistry and History & Citizenship it is noted that she was 'not active' during the teacher-led portions and that she is 'too quiet'. In the Chemistry lesson, the observer suggested that she 'was seemingly focused'. In History & Citizenship, it is noted that she didn't raise her hand at all in the lesson. In the activities too, it is noted that she is not engaged. In Chemistry she observed to be looking at the board, while in History & Citizenship she is described as 'distracted'.

The teachers' favourites (Gianna, Samantha, Immaculée)

Overview of the **Teachers' favourites** typology

General demographics: the three girls were from the urban (Nyarugenge) and relatively rural (Ruhango) districts and were 16 or 17 years old. They attend school regularly, including quiet revision time before school.

Attainment: identified by their teachers as high achieving in English, and they are on track to achieve a merit or distinction. It is expected that they will all transition to upper secondary education.

In-class activity: in the classroom, they are observed as fully engaged and talking regularly. They are repeatedly called upon by teachers, they ask questions, they are given opportunities to summarise. Shame or lack of confidence does not come up for these girls.

Support mechanisms: Teachers evidently important in these girls' educational experiences, and they speak positively about teachers in their interviews. Because teachers play a major role in their study and success, they are happy to ask questions of their teachers. They have time and space to revise, including some memorisation if they think the subject demands it. They choose to spend time with peers who are also doing well and who are similarly competitive.

Home life: Compared to other girls in the sample, they have relatively low levels of home chores. Two of the three have low financial challenges and are living in relatively secure home environments. Teachers describe them as having supportive homes.

Role of English: These girls practice their English in class in different ways (summarising, asking questions etc) but observations suggest they could be encouraged to take more risks and it is possible they are not being pushed to the same sort of English language use as the highest performing boys. These girls seem to be doing the best across all subjects and are seen to be 'good' at English, reinforcing the idea that being educated and being able to converse in English are interconnected.

Gianna is 16 years old and one of the top achieving girls in secondary three in a school in Nyarugenge, one of three districts in the capital city of Kigali and the richest district in the country. Nyarugenge has one of the highest enrolment rates in the country for girls in Primary and lower Secondary. One in ten girls scored a distinction in the 2018 Primary Six English National Examinations and distinction rates were also the highest in the country for girls in the Secondary three English National Examinations. At Gianna's school, girls tend to outperform boys in English at both the primary and lower secondary levels.

She is described by her teachers as a bright and conscientious girl. She was admitted to a public boarding school after her good grades in P6 but didn't like the life there so her parents agreed for her to join a day school near her home. Gianna is studying hard to pass the national exams and be admitted into an excellent boarding school where she wants to study Maths, chemistry and biology at Advanced level.

At home she revises from 6pm – 8pm alone. She likes to study biology and history and revise at home because it's quiet. She studies these subjects at home because they are easier for her and if she's taken good notes, all she needs is some time to memorise them in a quiet place. For these she doesn't need exercises and formulas with other learners. Her parents encourage her to study hard and they follow up in a way that doesn't accept time watching movies or other distracting activities. She is also motivated by seeing people who have studied successfully and have a good life thanks to education. She likes to hear these success stories.

At school, Gianna likes paying attention to the teachers and asking questions when she doesn't understand something. At school, she likes to study maths, chemistry and physics because these are the subjects, she requires more support with and in school she can get support from teachers and classmates with whom she discusses and does exercises. She dislikes the noise and stories from her classmates who talk when the teacher is not there and narrate movies. She is motivated by her teacher who teaches Maths and physics (because he explains well and helps her pass the lesson) and her parents. She usually arrives in the morning for self-study/revision time from 6:30 to 7:20 before lessons with the teachers because it is generally quiet during this time with fewer learners only arriving when the classes start.

During classroom observations, Gianna is described as active in the Maths and History & Citizenship lessons, but not active in Biology and Geography. In Maths, it was noted that she was listening and that she raised her hand and contributed when the teacher asked questions. In the activity, though, she appeared to be following but did not write. In History & Citizenship Gianna was actively following and raising her hand. She was sometimes busy looking in the book. During the teacher-led portion of the lesson she did not talk to others but was busy reading her notebook. She was engaged in the History & Citizenship activity and contributed an answer successfully. In Biology, she did not raise her hand but was selected at random to answer a question, but she was unable to give the correct answer. The teacher encouraged her to stand up and try again. In the Biology activity she was focused on writing. During Geography, she was focused on taking notes from the board.

Immaculée is one of the top achieving girls in secondary three in a school in Nyarugenge, one of three districts in the capital city of Kigali and the richest district in the country. Nyarugenge has one of the highest enrolment rates in the country for girls in Primary and lower Secondary. One in ten girls scored a distinction in the 2018 Primary Six English National Examinations and distinction rates were also the highest in the country for girls in the Secondary three English National Examinations. At Immaculée's school, girls tend to outperform boys in English at both the primary and lower secondary levels.

Immaculée does well in all subjects but is particularly good at music which she hopes to study from S4 and spends a lot of time reading English storybooks which she borrows from the library. Immaculée likes to study biology because it teaches her about living things such as how plants grow. She also enjoys Maths. She enjoys it when the teacher gives exercises to check their understanding and makes corrections amongst them. She likes both these courses because she sees them as related to everyday life. She doesn't enjoy Chemistry but doesn't know why she finds it difficult, saying it's just not her course. Immaculée likes to be able to concentrate in class on what the teachers are saying. She says that she hates it when students ask nonsense questions and disturb the teachers and that generally it's too noisy which gets in the way of learning, causing the teacher to stop teaching and makes them lose time. She likes to study from 7-10 in the morning when her head is fresh and stress free. She says she can memorise very well in the morning, before she's had math or other courses in her head. Immaculée says that at home she is alone studying because there is nobody who can help her because her sister and neighbours are at boarding school. She is the eldest of the children

at home and she has some small amounts of housework, but she says it doesn't bother her and she still has free time in the evening to study. At home, Immaculée likes to study biology and entrepreneurship. This is something her mother can give her help with and sometimes she asks her mother about how much money she would need to start a business. Her mother encourages her to learn and to study. Immaculée's mother sells rice and it's easy for her to go to her mother's work and pick up money if she needs it for something. The things that distract her are TV and films because she puts her notebooks aside and watches them with others because she cannot resist them. She talks a lot about her physical health and mentions a lot of pain associated with menstruation. This gets in the way of her studies, sometimes she takes medicine and other times she goes home.

Immaculée and her friends revise their learning on the way home from school by asking one another questions about the content learned that day. They randomly choose questions and who should answer them to really test themselves. She says this helps them to learn the content by heart. She says that people on the way to and from school motivate her to learn because they talk about how they used to go to school and now they have 'this and that'. She also likes singing gospel or RnB music with friends on the way because this refreshes her mind and helps her to relax.

During classroom observations, Immaculée is observed to be generally active, but particularly so in Maths, when it is noted that she was paying attention to the explanations the teacher gave. She volunteered to copy a question onto the board from the book, but when she did this she was very quiet. In the Maths activity, she did not appear fully engaged, but she was listening and writing. In Biology, Immaculée is described as 'sometimes active'. She did raise her hand to contribute but she failed. Other times she was busy taking notes. She was focused on the Biology activity and was observed writing. In Geography, Immaculée raised her hand to contribute and was chosen by the teacher three times, including giving an answer about the importance of fishing. In History & Citizenship, Immaculée was concentrating and following, repeatedly raising her hand. In the activity, she was focused and concentrated in the secretary role and contributed to the presentation.

Samantha is the top achieving girl in her secondary three class in a school in Ruhango district, a relatively rural district with middling poverty levels and very low incidences of gender-based bias in the community. Girls in Ruhango had among the lowest average failure rates compared to the national picture and with only a 6% gap in the proportion that passed English compared to boys. Samantha attends a school which is rural, but not remote, and where girls and boys have broadly similar English results at the end of both primary and lower secondary school.

Samantha lives in a poor family. Her parents are described by Samantha's teachers as caring very much about her education. Samantha's family home was destroyed by a natural disaster in 2018 and someone provided a small house for them to live temporarily. She feels that without this temporary shelter she would not have been able to continue studying. She is grateful to have electricity at home which allows her to study in the evening without difficulty. She discusses her father as someone who is old and poor but who tries hard to use his physical energy to earn money for her education. He carries sand for people, and this provides money for pens and notebooks. He encourages her and helps her with Kinyarwanda and some mathematics. He tells her that she is the one who will improve their lives when she finishes her studies and gets a job. She feels an obligation to her family to achieve this and to make more effort in order to be important to her family one day.

Samantha says she has classmates who help her enjoy learning. Many of them she's studied with since the beginning of primary school and they are friends that she likes to be with. Samantha likes group discussion, study and revision at school because she can be the one to explain to others and to help them do their exercises. This gives her courage to study better than them so that she can be ready to help when they ask her. She enjoys Chemistry most

because it's the easiest subject for her and she is the best performer in the subject. She knows that she is the best performing student in Chemistry and that this makes the boys unhappy with her. Samantha thinks that the boys are constantly monitoring what she does, and they think it's negative that she often asks questions in class. She feels that they don't view her question asking as being about wanting to understand, but rather that she wants to demonstrate to the teacher that she's the best learner. Samantha says that this feeling extends to the way they feel about the teachers, that they dislike teachers who ask her to answer questions or give presentations. This doesn't seem to impact the way she herself feels about her teachers. She likes that they encourage her to study hard, particularly the physics and entrepreneurship teachers who she says care much for her. She finds Maths difficult and says she doesn't understand it. She wishes that the teacher could use different methods that would better facilitate her learning, though she doesn't know what those might be. Samantha is grateful for the girls' room at school where she is able to get a sanitary pad because her parents cannot purchase them for her. If the school doesn't have any, she goes home and misses some classes.

During classroom observations, Samantha is described as 'very active' during the teacher-led portions of all lessons and is described as 'engaged' in all activities, except in Chemistry. In all lessons, she raised her hand to contribute and the observer notes that she is frequently called upon by the teacher and that her contributions were successful. In History & Citizenship, it is noted that she raised her hand more than 4 times and she spoke for more than 3 minutes explaining the history of revolution in France. In Geography, she answered a question about the causes of deforestation. In Biology, it was noted that Samantha was focused and following the explanations while the teacher was talking. For the Biology activities, she worked in a pair with the student next to her and Samantha was observed writing as well as contributing to write an answer on the board in the feedback. In Geography it is noted that she was focused and engaged and collaborating with Nazou.

Those with multiple strategies (Kalisa, Aurore, Audrey, Vestine)

Overview of the **Using Multiple Strategies** typology

General demographics: three of the four girls come from the very rural school in Kirehe district, the other from Nyarugenge district in Kigali. They are 16 and 17 years old. They generally attend regularly.

Attainment: They are expected to pass their English examinations and transition to upper secondary education.

In-class activity: these girls are mostly engaged in following content and consistently respond to closed questions and are sometimes called upon by the teacher. They are not asking questions, taking risks or being promoted to try again.

Support mechanisms: these girls have access to and employ multiple strategies to support them in their learning. They have access to varying types of resource to help them, such as English books and have quiet time at home to revise and do homework. They rely heavily on peer mutual support to keep up with the curriculum. The teacher is one of a number of resources they draw on.

Home life: At home, they have relatively low burdens with some or no chores. All but one regularly manage to do school revision at home. Only one girl in this group has high financial challenges and all live in relatively secure home environments.

Role of English: While these girls do not talk explicitly about language as a barrier, they do rely on a variety of strategies to keep up. Given the type of talk they are doing in the classroom, they may access content but it is unlikely they are developing their English language.

Kalisa is 16 years old and attends secondary three in a rural school in one of the most rural districts in Rwanda – Kirehe. In Kirehe, there are higher than average community-based gender biases and enrolment rates are lower for both girls and boys than the national average. The vast majority of girls are scoring a 40-49% in the P6 English exam; by S3, Kirehe has the highest failure rate in the English exam for anywhere in the country. This would suggest that English language is a particularly major barrier to learning in this district, with many girls ‘just passing’ moving into ‘failing’ by the end of S3. Teachers at Kalisa’s school suggest that girls are more affected by both the language of learning and teaching and out-of-school factors than boys. They say that girls face more disturbances such as being harassed by boys/men and family conflict. Kalisa is expected to pass her English and other S3 examinations.

Kalisa is described by her teachers as a very disciplined learner who can improve her performance even more. At school, Kalisa depends on her teachers, peers and individual study time to learn effectively. She says she likes studying English and her English teacher who encourages them to work hard. The English teacher comes to school early in the morning to support them during self-study time and gives them advice, which motivates her to study. She says she understands it well and performs well in the subject. She likes learning Maths, Chemistry, Biology in groups and enjoys collaborating with classmates who can help her understand her lessons. She wants to study Biology, Chemistry Geography combination at

Advanced level. Learning in groups helps her understand the subjects and to perform well. In the past they did revision individually and she says the brighter learners wouldn't help others and they themselves remained the best performers. Their Kinyarwanda teacher told them that this kind of competition will not serve them well and advised them instead to help one another as a team to successfully prepare for their national exams. Now they are learning to help one another, to find tests and exams from other schools and previous national exams to revise them together. She hopes that this will help one another to pass these exams. Kalisa dislikes the noise in the classroom which prevents her from concentrating. She says that sometimes teachers hinder her learning. Another distraction is students who are telling stories during self-learning time. She feels motivated to study when she sees educated people who have different jobs. She tells herself that education will help her to have a job and to be self-reliant like them.

At home, Kalisa mainly revises Geography and History in order to memorise the content. Kalisa's parents give her the school materials she needs to learn. Her mother especially encourages her to study hard and gives her time for revision at home. Her mother is a community health worker who is gone from home sometimes. When her mother is away, Kalisa cooks, feeds the cows and cleans, but when her mother is home, she does most of the work, making time for Kalisa to revise. Kalisa's father is old, and her mother is his second wife. His children by his widow do not recognise Kalisa and her brother as their siblings and they refuse to help. They have their own families. Her father cannot work, and when her mother doesn't have money for school fees, there is nobody else she can turn to. She is tired at night and the evening home activities make her tired so that when she starts revising, she falls asleep. Some people discourage Kalisa by telling her that her mother will not be able to afford boarding school fees, so she is studying in vain. Her mother tells her she will try her best to help.

On the way to school, Kalisa likes chatting with other learners, telling stories related to learning or other things. She doesn't like traveling alone because there is a man, she sees sometimes on the way who she fears. She waits for people to walk with so that he doesn't beat her.

Kalisa is observed as most engaged in the Maths lesson. She is also engaged in the Chemistry lesson, though it is noted that she follows the teacher without speaking. The observer notes that Kalisa is trying to be engaged in Chemistry and during one activity she does try to provide a solution to a question on the board, but her answer is incorrect. The male student who correctly answered the previous question is asked to help her and he gives the correct answer. In History & Citizenship she is described as 'following passively' during teacher-led portions. In activities it is observed that she is following with her notebook on her thigh and that she sometimes takes notes, but she is also observed losing concentration when the teacher talks for too long. Like others, Kalisa is described as not being actively engaged in the Geography lesson. She does volunteer to give an example in answer to a question from notes that they had taken prior to the lesson.

Aurore is 16 years old and attends secondary three in a rural school in one of the most rural districts in Rwanda – Kirehe. In Kirehe, there are higher than average community-based gender biases and enrolment rates are lower for both girls and boys than the national average. The vast majority of girls are scoring a 40-49% in the P6 English exam; by S3, Kirehe has the highest failure rate in the English exam for anywhere in the country. This would suggest that English language is a particularly major barrier to learning in this district, with many girls 'just passing' moving into 'failing' by the end of S3. Teachers at Gisele's school suggest that girls are more affected by both the language of learning and teaching and out-of-school factors than boys. They say that girls face more disturbances such as being harassed by boys/men and family conflict. Aurore is expected to pass her English and other S3 examinations.

Aurore is described as a learner who attends very regularly. Her teachers report that there is a good relationship between the school and her parents who often visit the school. At home, Aurore says that she has a lot of household chores which frustrates her. However, she also says that her brother who is a motorist stays at home so that she can join her classmates at school for self-organised revision sessions. Time to revise with her peers is very important to Aurore. She also finds some time at home to revise independently, particularly enjoying entrepreneurship because she can read and understand it by herself. Aurore likes when her father has time to teach her French and she finds this motivating to her studies. When she is not working, she likes it when her parents and siblings are all at home chatting and sharing food and drinks and playing.

Aurore says that her studies are sometimes impeded by poverty when she doesn't have all the materials she requires. Lack of access to books is also a barrier. While there is a library, she says that they refuse to give out books. Teachers come to class with the one book they use, except Kiswahili and literature. She cannot understand why books are kept in the library when they need them. The lack of materials in the girls' room is something that bothers her. She says that the room is there for when they need it during their period, but access to it is refused. It's meant for use when the girls have a lot of pain and need to rest, but they cannot use it for this. When they ask for pads, they are told that the room key is lost. When this happens, she decides instead to go back home.

At school, Aurore likes studying history because she likes the subject and passes with good grades. Working in groups of active learners helps her a lot because when every member can contribute, they can help one another. She explains what she knows, and she also learns from others' explanations or exercises. She likes the history teacher because the teacher takes time to talk about ordinary life and to advise them. Through this, they learn values such as self-respect and respect for others. Aurore feels that this helps her to avoid misbehaving or being misled by peer pressure. Aurore is bothered by teachers who unfairly use corporal punishment. She says that some of the teachers beat students a lot, neither do they listen to the students before beating. Beating punishments are given for lateness and not paying fees. She acknowledges that the negative impact of this is fearful students and she herself feels scared to attend school when she thinks she might get beaten.

During classroom observations, she is described as not consistently well engaged. During teacher-led sections in Chemistry and History & Citizenship she is observed taking notes while the teacher talks, but in Mathematics and Geography it is noted that she is not always actively engaged. Aurore seems to make the greatest effort to participate in Mathematics when she raises her hand to volunteer answers to evaluation questions. In the three other subjects it is noted that she is sometimes chatting with others in Kinyarwanda during the activities. In Chemistry she is observed actively engaging in the evaluation activity.

Vestine is a shy 17 year old who attends secondary three in a school in Nyarugenge, one of three districts in the capital city of Kigali and the richest district in the country. Nyarugenge has one of the highest enrolment rates in the country for girls in Primary and lower Secondary. One in ten girls scored a distinction in the 2018 Primary Six English National Examinations and distinction rates were also the highest in the country for girls in the Secondary three English National Examinations. At Vestine's school, girls tend to outperform boys in English at both the primary and lower secondary levels. Vestine says that she scores around 50% (a pass) in her English examinations.

Vestine lives with her uncle, but the reason for this is not explained. It is not clear the makeup of her family or if she has siblings. She doesn't mention house chores or responsibilities. Despite this, she says that her father helps her with English and Math during the holidays. Vestine is often sent out of school to collect the school fees when her parents don't pay. Her parents are not able to pay her fees and this impacts on her attendance as she regularly

misses lessons when she is sent home to get fees. This may have a significant impact on her given that she is achieving in the 50s even when she is not able to attend regularly.

She likes to study at home then in her free time listen to music or read 'soft' or small books, but she hates when someone is yelling at her or stopping her from reading or reading. Listening to music helps her relax and she does this because she says she can't study all the time and needs time to relax. The books she enjoys reading are love stories, life stories and things related to the human body because she likes Biology. She reads books in English because this helps her to improve her vocabulary and learn English well. She studies in the evenings to go over the content they've covered in every lesson. She feels that if she doesn't that the amount of learning will pile up and she will not recall it. She says she needs to do this to stay on the same page and not get lazy and she worries that if she didn't, that her marks would slip because even with this practice, she is achieving only around 50%.

Vestine likes to study at school early in the morning around 6:30 during independent study time. She likes to study with her friends and to chat with them about what they learned in the day because they help each other capture well while learning. She says that they discuss their dreams which motivates them to learn. Vestine likes learning physics because this is life and biology because it helps her to understand her reproductive health. She hates it when people interfere with her studying or disturb her because then she cannot concentrate and cannot memorize content from the lessons, for which she needs a quiet place. Vestine talks quite a bit about how love interests distract her at school. She doesn't mention anyone specifically but says that it's distraction to be 'going in love' with a classmate or student at the same school. Not having enough material to study at school or not having fees gets in the way of her learning.

On the way to school, Vestine chats to her friend on the way to school or reads small books on the journey. She hates it when someone stops her on her way to school, for example stopping her and asking what she is up to. She says she especially hates it when boys do this because they make her late to school or home and as a consequence, she cannot revise her lessons.

Vestine is very shy and says she doesn't like to speak in class which her teachers suggest is because of poor concentration. However, in observations, Vestine is observed as being active in the Maths, Geography and History & Citizenship lessons. In Biology she was focused on taking notes of the explanations from the board. While she did not raise her hand, the teacher aimed to include Vestine in the lesson and encouraged her to respond. When she was selected randomly to answer a question she answered correctly. In Geography, although she was active, it was once when she raised her hand to read. In the Maths activity, she was observed to be engaged as she was writing. In History & Citizenship, she was the secretary in the group activity and contributed to the presentation. She also raised her hand to contribute during the lesson conclusion.

Audrey is 16 years old and attends secondary three in a rural school in one of the most rural districts in Rwanda – Kirehe. In Kirehe, there are higher than average community-based gender biases and enrolment rates are lower for both girls and boys than the national average. The vast majority of girls are scoring a 40-49% in the P6 English exam; by S3, Kirehe has the highest failure rate in the English exam for anywhere in the country. This would suggest that English language is a particularly major barrier to learning in this district, with many girls 'just passing' moving into 'failing' by the end of S3. Teachers at Gisele's school suggest that girls are more affected by both the language of learning and teaching and out-of-school factors than boys. They say that girls face more disturbances such as being harassed by boys/men and family conflict. Audrey is one of the only students at the school who is expected to pass her English and other S3 examinations with a merit.

Audrey attends regularly, participates in class and completes all of her homework and assignments outside of class hours. Audrey feels supported by her parents, who she says give her the time and resources she needs to study. Her father has a stationery store. He gives her his mobile phone she needs access to the internet, which has through work. She uses this to revise Geography or do homework that requires research. She is distracted by the TV at home when her father brings home movies to watch in the evenings. This happens when she is trying to revise, and she loses concentration. He allows her to watch the film so long as she revises before going to bed, but this causes her to go to sleep late.

At school, Audrey likes studying all subjects, especially Maths, physics and chemistry because her sisters help her to learn these subjects as they have studied them at Advanced level and graduated in science from university. Audrey is bothered by the change in teachers which happened after the school closures and lockdown. Some of her teachers were transferred to a new school and teachers arrived at her school. These teachers began new units without completing the ones they were studying with their outgoing teachers. Other than this, Audrey does not talk about her teachers very much.

During break times, she and her classmates go outside and chat and play to relax and refresh their minds. The noise in class disturbs her learning, particularly when the teacher is not in class. She finds that this sometimes makes her waste time without studying. At school, there are different clubs such as 'Ni Nyampinga' club where they learn about reproductive health and how they can behave at different stages of their development. She values this as useful education and appreciates having this kind of instruction. There is one classmate in particular, another girl, whose friendship she highly values as this student's encouragement helps her to study hard and keep focus. Audrey is waiting to go to the ophthalmologist for glasses because she has a sight problem that is making her eyes sensitive to light. This is getting in the way of her reading. She applies some medicine for this, but she hopes that glasses will help her to study without problem in the future.

During classroom observations, Audrey, like others, seems to be most actively engaged in the Maths lesson, although she is also observed to be actively engaged in Geography and raising her hand to answer the teacher's questions (though not called upon). In Chemistry she is described as 'not actively engaged' and in History & Citizenship it is noted that she appears to be listening and looking at the teacher and the board. In Mathematics, during an activity Audrey raises her hand and is selected to answer a question about angles, which she does correctly. In Chemistry she appears to be quietly following during activities but with no signs of active engagement. The observer notes that during activities in History & Citizenship, Audrey looks 'absent-minded'. She tries to answer one of the evaluation questions, but she repeats what another learner had said because she was not following. In the evaluation activity in Geography, Audrey seems to be well engaged and gets 10 out of 10, but it is noted that she is copying the answers from her notebook. She is selected by the teacher to write one importance of mining in Africa, and she writes, 'many can get job'.

Those going against the odds (Francoise, Nazou, Tressy, Uwineza)

Overview of the **Going against the odds** typology

General demographics: The four girls range in age from 16-19 years. The girls are from three of the four sampled districts, rather than clustering in a particular district (Burera, Ruhango and Nyarugenge). They are mostly regular attenders.

Attainment: Teachers have identified them as on track to achieve a pass in English, or potentially higher. It appears that they may transition if their circumstances allow, and based on the rest of the picture, it seems that they are likely to do everything in their ability to stay in school and transition, but may not be able to do so.

In-class activity: these girls are consistently engaged and despite not being regularly called upon, they put their hands up, ask questions and they want the teachers' attention, though they often do not get it. This limits the type of talk they are engaged in.

Support mechanisms: they do not have clear support mechanisms or social networks. They see themselves as outsiders and talk repeatedly of other people being jealous of them and not taking them seriously. They are their own support – grabbing some information from another learner, snatching time to do some revision. Two of the girls have their personal sources of financial support (hens/goats). Teachers are not a big source in their learning.

Home life: these girls all have some home burdens, ranging from significant household chores, financial challenges and living in insecure home environments.

Role of English: these girls see English as a key determinant of being better educated and see it as a motivating factor, or even another stick that they berate themselves with. It might be that English is stopping them from being 'pushed on' by the teacher. Our question is whether, in a non-English medium of instruction classroom, might they be getting to another level.

Francoise is 16 years old and attends secondary three in Burera. She is regularly absent from school but remains on track to pass her S3 exams, including English. Burera is one of the most rural and poorest districts in Rwanda where gender-based bias is amongst the highest in the country. While enrolment is very high for girls in Burera at primary level, this changes in lower secondary where the enrolment rate is below average for girls and boys. Girls in Burera have the lowest chance of a distinction at S3 English or anywhere in the country and the widest failure gap between boys and girls. Francoise's school is very rural and in an area of high poverty. Girls at the school also have high demands on their time due to household chores, often missing parts of the school day.

Francoise lives with her mother and siblings. Her mother has a cleaning job, but her income is small, and she sometimes finds it difficult to feed her children. Francoise is sometimes absent from class when she is assigned other activities by her mother to support the household. Francoise has at least two elder siblings, but they no longer live at home. She seems to have some younger siblings, saying that she is now the eldest child at home, though

she doesn't mention how many others are at home now. Her mother encourages her to learn so that she can manage to be independent and self-reliant like her older brother and sister. She says she likes peace and freedom because when she has troubles at home this makes it difficult for her to study. She likes her hen because when it lays eggs, she is able to sell them and with this money buys school supplies such as pens and notebooks. She has also learnt to do some cloth weaving, which she learnt from her elder sister. This generates some money and helps her cater for her basic needs. She likes revising in the evenings around her housework. Because she is the eldest child at home, she does most of the work. This includes fetching water, collecting firewood, preparing food, sweeping and washing.

Francoise talks a lot about jealous neighbours, that they are not happy to know that the children in her family are performing better than their own. She says that they are jealous because all her siblings attend school and perform well. They discourage her and tell her that she is studying hard in vain and that she should drop out and cultivate because her good performance will be useless, that her poor family will not be able to support her if she is admitted to a good school. She says she doesn't like playing with people who have not studied. There seems to be some emphasis on differentiating between people who have studied and those who have not. Francoise says she is motivated by educated people who have been successful and gotten a job because she believes that if she completes her studies successfully, she will also find a job and become like them.

Francoise likes Biology because it teaches her about life, and she has learned a lot from the lessons on reproduction. It is the only lesson she mentions. She says this helped her know herself and how she should behave. Francoise participates in independent study from 6:30 – 7:55 in the morning at school. Francoise sits with learners who she says are brighter than her and they help her to understand the content and to do exercises. She says she likes self-confidence and knows that her family is poor, but that she has confidence and trust in her education that it will help her to become self-reliant and to improve her parents' living condition. By revising in the morning and evening, her main aim is to perform well and has in mind that this will lead to a bright future and her family's well-being. Francoise mentions that she dislikes being frightened and punished by teachers, particularly male teachers including those of Kiswahili and Kinyarwanda who used to beat them. She says that she was afraid of him and did not like the subject he teaches. She is also troubled when she has to miss some lessons because parents have not been able to pay the fees. She feels pity for learners and other people with bad behavior such as learners who misbehave or drunk men and women.

During classroom observations, Francoise is observed in all lessons to be actively listening and engaged. In Biology, she actively discusses with her partner, and it is Francoise who represents her pair during the oral feedback. In Geography, when the teacher asks her a question she responds. She is also selected to summarise the lesson and does so very well, remembering all the details. During the evaluation activity in the History & Citizenship lesson Francoise was among only 3 girls to be selected to go to the board to write two changes brought by the colonizers. In Mathematics, she raised her hand to volunteer to answer Q2 and she wrote the calculation on the board and explained her answer in English.

Nazou is a determined 19-year-old who attends secondary three in Ruhango district, a relatively rural district with middling poverty levels and very low incidences of gender-based bias in the community. Girls in Ruhango had among the lowest average failure rates compared to the national picture and with only a 6% gap in the proportion that passed English compared to boys. Nazou attends a school which is rural, but not remote, and where girls and boys have broadly similar English results at the end of both primary and lower secondary school.

Nazou is described by her teachers as a student that used to attend regularly and achieved well but is now at risk of dropping out. Due to the school closures, she has been having short-term jobs of supporting in construction. Her teachers say that she is no longer willing to study hard. Instead, she is looking to engage in more money-making activities, and her teachers say that she has started to engage in relationships with boys which they also suggest has negatively affected her performance.

Nazou lives with both of her parents. Financially, she contributes to a money savings group comprised of students her own age. Her parents give money towards this each week, and this helps the collective, especially in times when parents don't have money. This is how she managed to get a goat. She sees her goat and cow as important to financial needs for school. Nazou herself says that she has recently done some sex work in exchange for food. She says she has stopped doing this because she realised it was affecting her performance.

Nazou has at least two siblings, one who is older and one younger than herself. She likes her parents, especially her mother who is home with her all the time and to whom she can tell her stories. She does hide things from her mother about her personal and sexual relationships or struggles related to her studies when she isn't 'performing well' because she doesn't want the information getting to her father who sometimes hits her. She says her father drives a motorcycle and is mostly away from home and often tired. Nazou revises from 3AM at home but also does self-study from 6:30 – 8:00 AM at school.

She says that poverty at home disrupts her learning (not having access to needed materials, both academic and sanitary/personal). The lack of sanitary products sometimes keeps her at home. She doesn't mention doing housework or chores. Her sister got pregnant at 17 years old and dropped out of school after having the baby because she was discouraged, and her life changed. The father of the baby got married to another woman. She hates the people of her village who are disrespectful and those who discourage her. She hates people who discourage her, who tell her that she shouldn't study because she won't get a job or people from her village who say that even if she gets her diploma that she will leave school and 'cultivate' (i.e., have children). She feels motivated by seeing diplomats who have jobs and seeing people who look beautiful and who have office jobs. She is motivated by the village leader, who she says tells her she is a strong person and encourages her to focus on her studies and to drop the distractions.

Nazou has experienced a lot of sexual pressure and there seem to be plenty of opportunities for encounters. She had a boyfriend but left him because she said he tried to rule her and thought she should obey everything he said. She conveyed this experience with an older man with whom she was engaged in an abusive relationship that led to impacting her personal and school life. She believes that when you mix this kind of life with your studies, you will fail. She shares that during this time, she slipped from 5th or 6th place in class down to 26th because it was a distraction to her, but after she stopped the relationship, she says she was able to get back up to 14th place in the following term.

Nazou says she enjoys studying Math and Chemistry and learning Physics, Biology, Chemistry and Maths. She says she hates teachers who ignore her when she asks questions and who won't translate into Kinyarwanda. Nazou says that she likes it when she eats at school because this helps her learn with courage, but she realises that many classmates can't eat because this costs money. She is grateful to have been elected for students' welfare and now she eats for free. She comes to school early to study between 6:30 and 8AM when the air is fresh and there are few people around and this makes it easier to memorise. She says she hates teachers who ignore her when she asks questions or when she doesn't get a straight answer from them. Nazou likes revising and learning with others in small groups because they can help each other. She worries about losing self confidence in class when she's called on. Nazou wants to be a math teacher or nurse.

Nazou likes chatting with students from other schools as she walks to her own school because she says her own classmates underestimate her. Nazou says she hates meeting people on the way home from school who try to give her free travel and businessmen/vendors. She says she hates when people offer to give her a lift then they end up taking her where they want, they suggest going out and say they love her, promise her goods and that she will want for nothing if they live together and eventually you give them what they want, which she says is sex.

During classroom observations, Nazou is described as 'very active' during the teacher-led portions of 3 out of 4 lessons. In the remaining lesson, History & Citizenship, she was described as 'active' but it was also noted that she was talking to her neighbours. Nazou is observed as contributing during teacher-led questions in all lessons. Her answers are not always correct, but it is noted that she doesn't appear to be discouraged as she continues to raise her hand. This pattern is noted in both Chemistry and History & Citizenship. In H&C, there was an example where she failed to answer in English, but the teacher encouraged her to continue in Kinyarwanda. In Geography it is noted that her contributions were in Kinyarwanda and that she was focused and writing notes when the teacher was explaining on the board. Nazou was also engaged in all activities. In Biology she represented her group and presented their findings. In Chemistry she participated in the feedback correction of the activity and in Geography she raised her hand to contribute to the discussion of the activity but was not selected. In History & Citizenship, Nazou is observed collaborating and writing with Samantha [Girl A], who was sitting near her. At one point in the Geography lesson, Nazou asked a question, "What is the difference between vegetation and climate?" Rather than answer herself, the teacher encouraged a student to answer and Samantha answered the question.

Tressy is 17 years old and attends secondary three in a school in Nyarugenge, one of three districts in the capital city of Kigali and the richest district in the country. Nyarugenge has one of the highest enrolment rates in the country for girls in Primary and lower Secondary. One in ten girls scored a distinction in the 2018 Primary Six English National Examinations and distinction rates were also the highest in the country for girls in the Secondary three English National Examinations. At Tressy's school, girls tend to outperform boys in English at both the primary and lower secondary levels. Tressy says that she scores around 50% (a pass) in her English examinations.

Tressy has a good relationship with her mother but lives with her father because he is the one who is able to help her in schooling and buy materials. She says that he doesn't really pay the school fees even though he is able to because he does not prioritise school fees over other expenditure. More generally, her parents encourage her to study and motivate her to learn, but she says they also put pressure on her. Tressy says that her father, in particular, tells her the benefit of learning and how it will help her in the future. He also helps her with her lessons at home, especially physics and science related subjects because he can explain things related to electricity because of his job. This motivates her to put effort into her studies, especially as she is the only one in day school. Her sister is at boarding school.

Tressy likes 'thinking about herself' and tackling difficult lessons and doing what she can to understand them. She doesn't like it when visitors tell her she will not be able to succeed in the subjects she has chosen for S4. She says she feels capable of taking these on and feels confident that she can do well, but dislikes people trying to dissuade and discourage her. At home, she revises for physics because it is the subject she understands. She prefers to study in the morning at the weekend after the housework before she gets tired. Sometimes,

housework gets in the way of her studies, for example when she has to cook beans because this takes a long time.

At school, Tressy likes it when the teacher tells them how to study well and tells them what they can get from school. She enjoys it when there is time for the teachers to chat with them during lessons or tell them stories. She says they sometimes do this in the afternoon when there is so much sunshine and this helps them get back to the lesson and concentrate. Her Physics teacher does this, but also French and Math and sometimes her English teacher when the students are making noise. She likes learning with understanding, saying 'I like this so much'. Tressy likes to work with other students because they can give her explanation when she revises, particularly Maths because she finds this the most difficult subject and people can help her when she studies this at school. She really dislikes it when her classmates discourage her from signing up for the difficult courses in S4. While they may feel the subjects are complicated, Tressy explains that she has confidence that she is capable of learning them. Tressy likes doing Maths at school because here she can get people to help her. However, sometimes, she explains, they will not help her because they are jealous and don't want her to get better grades than them. Tressy was absent during the observation lessons due to sickness.

On the way to school, Tressy takes note of students from the best schools and finds motivation in observing them. She says she uses this to think about what she can do to improve her own learning and to have the same knowledge level as those students and get admitted into the best schools. Friends tell her endless stories that are useless, and this distracts her from getting home in time, delaying her until 17:30. Tressy seems to get a great amount of joy and pleasure from learning and understanding things well and to challenge herself to tackle difficult subjects or topics. She says that she considers what she will do when her father is no longer alive, and this motivates her to work hard at school.

Uwineza is 15 years old and attends secondary three in Burera, one of the most rural and poorest districts in Rwanda where gender-based bias is amongst the highest in the country. While enrolment is very high for girls in Burera at primary level, this changes in lower secondary where the enrolment rate is below average for girls and boys. Girls in Burera have the lowest chance of a distinction at S3 English or anywhere in the country and the widest failure gap between boys and girls. Uwineza's school is very rural and in an area of high poverty. Girls at the school also have high demands on their time due to household chores, often missing parts of the school day.

Uwineza is very motivated and finds time to revise different subjects at home despite having a lot of housework. Her duties include fetching grass for the cows and feeding them, cooking, washing, and sweeping. She is the eldest child and does most of the work. Her father helps her collect food for the cows when he is at home and her mother cooks when she is not at home. When Uwineza is at home, her mother is busy with other farming activities. Uwineza says that while she knows her family is poor her parents encourage her to attend school because if she is lucky and finishes successfully, she will get a job and help them improve their living conditions.

Uwineza says that she likes her fellow learners because they help her to learn when they ask her to explain some content to them. She says that her classmates trust her and believe that she understands the lessons. They ask her to help explain lessons to them during the school holidays or in free time. This encourages her to work hard because when she is explaining, she masters the lessons. She likes all her subjects but pays more attention to Chemistry

because she needs more support from the teacher and fellow learners in this subject and can only get this support at school.

Uwineza recalls that they used to be allowed to go to the school during the holidays to study and revise together, or alone, or invite a teacher when they needed support. She liked this because it allowed her to get rid of her domestic work and to join others. She was one of the students who was selected to explain some subjects to others, and this helped her to master the content. This opportunity is no longer available to them because some students started bringing boyfriends to the school and on one occasion they were caught 'doing ill practice' and the school discontinued allowing students to come in the holidays because nobody could be there to monitor the behaviour. She comments that now she has to find time by finishing her home tasks quickly and affording herself some time for self-study and revision.

During classroom observations, Uwineza is described as active and engaged in all lessons and answered questions in all lessons, although she did not always raise her hand to volunteer, but rather was called upon by the teacher. When she answered questions, she was successful, although it seems her answers were sometimes short. In Biology, Uwineza represented her pair in an oral presentation.